

SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF MONTELUKAST SODIUM AND BILASTINE IN TABLET DOSAGE FORM BY SIMULTANEOUS EQUATION SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD

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Article History:

Received: 15- Aug -2022
Revised: 10- Sep- 2022
Accepted: 11- Oct-2022
First Published: 08-Nov-2022

Cite this Article as :

Pinkal Patel, Zinal A. Panchal, Patel Sweta, Alamas Shaikh "Simultaneous Estimation of Montelukast Sodium and Bilastine in Tablet Dosage Form By Simultaneous Equation Spectrophotometric Method ", *International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research*, Vol. 9, Issue 2, 2022, pp 34-43.
DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7307826>

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ABSTRACT

A precise, exact, cost effective technique for estimating Montelukast sodium and Bilastine simultaneously in several tablet definite volume has been evolved using the concept of simultaneous equation approach. Measurements of bilastine at 282 nm and montelukast at 344 nm in methanol form the basis of the approach. According to ICH guidelines, many analytical parameters including linearity, precision, accuracy, and toughness were determined. The concentration ranges of montelukast and bilastine, which are 2-12 g/ml and 4-24 g/ml, respectively, show linearity at their respective wavelengths. The method's validity was checked using statistics. The formulation of the analysis for montelukast and bilastine results expressed as a percentage of label claims were discovered to be 101.83% and 99.79%, respectively. The routine analysis of both medications can therefore be performed using the proposed approach.

Keywords: Montelukast Sodium, Bilastine, Simultaneous Equation Method

INTRODUCTION

Chemically, Montelukast Sodium (MONT) (S, E 2-(((1-(((1-(((1-(((1-(((1-(((1-((1-3-(2-(7-chloroquinolin-2-yl) vinyl) phenyl) 2-(2-hydroxypropan-2-yl) phenylpropylthio) methyl cyclopropyl acetic acid^{1,2}) LTRA is used to treat asthma in consistent state and to lessen the symptoms of seasonal allergies.³⁻⁵ A review of the literature finds that the Indian Pharmacopoeia 2010

recognises the assay of Montelukast Sodium in both tablet and bulk form.⁶ Chemically speaking, bilastine (BILA) is 2-[4-[2-[4-[1-(2-ethoxyethyl) benzimidazol-2-yl] piperidin-1-yl] ethyl] phenyl]. acid 2-methylpropanoic. It is a second-generation H1-antihistamine that can be used to treat the symptoms of allergic rhinitis and chronic urticaria.⁷ According to a review of the literature, analytical methods like UV spectrophotometer and HPLC can be used to evaluate montelukast in pharmaceutical dose forms. U.V spectrophotometry and HPLC procedures are the analytical techniques reported for the measurement of MONT and BILA alone as well as in combination with other medications.⁸⁻³⁷ A thorough literature review revealed that there is no reported spectrometric method for the detection of montelukast sodium and bilastine in the preparation of pharmaceuticals, this work's goal was to evolve and test a spectrophotometric analytical technique for measuring both medications.. According to the ICH criteria, the suggested approach has been optimised and validated.³⁸ In this study, a successful attempt has been made to measure both medicines concurrently utilising a UV spectrophotometer and the Simultaneous Equation approach. The objective of this study is to aid in regular quality control of bilastine and sodium montelukast in pharmaceutical formulation.

Fig 1: Montelukast Structure

Fig 2: Bilastine Structure

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Instrument

All the absorption spectra were recorded using a UV-VIS double beam spectrophotometer UV-1700, Shimadzu Corp., with 1 cm quartz cell. A Shimadzu electronic balance was used to weigh the drugs and other items (AX 200, Shimadzu Corp., and Japan).

Chemical agents & Components

SYMED LABS LTD. in Hyderabad, India provided free samples of the analytically pure drugs bilastine and montelukast sodium. The tablet formulation used in the trial was called Belatin-M Tablet and was produced by SYNOKEM Pharmaceuticals Ltd. in India. It contained the prescribed dosages of 20 mg Bilastine and 10 mg Montelukast Sodium. Methanol of analytical grade was used as the solvent (E. Merck, Mumbai, India).

Preparation of standard stock solution

Two separate 100 ml volumetric flasks, each containing 10 mg of MONT and BILA, were added to the stock solutions. Solids were dissolved in the flasks by swishing them. Methanol was used to boost the amounts to the required level, yielding 100 g/ml of each medication.

Selection of Analytical Wavelength

The simultaneous equation technique must be designed with the wavelength maxima of both medications in mind. The wavelength maxima of MONT are at 344 nm and BILA are at 282 nm, respectively, according to the overlapping spectra of MONT and BILA (10 g/ml). To create a simultaneous equation, the wavelengths of 344 nm and 282 nm were used. (See Figure 3)

Fig 3: Overlapping spectra of MONT and BILA

Standard Curves for MONT & BILA

With the use of methanol, the working standard solutions of MONT and BILA were properly diluted to produce final concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 g/ml of MONT and 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 g/ml of BILA, respectively. The solution spectra between 200 nm & 400 nm were studied. A correlation between absorbance and concentration was found by measuring the absorbance of solutions at wavelengths of 344 nm and 282 nm while using.

Figure 4: Calibration Curve of BILA at 282 nm

Figure 5: Calibration Curve of MONT at 344 nm

VALIDATION

Accuracy

The intraday and interday accuracy of the proposed technique was evaluated by measuring absorbance three times on the same day and three times on three different days for three different concentrations of MONT (6, 8, and 10 g/ml) and BILA (12, 16, and 20 g/ml). RSD was used to show the results. By repeatedly scanning and measuring the absorbance of solutions ($n = 6$) for MONT (6 g/ml) and BILA (12 g/ml), The instrument's accuracy was assessed, and %RSD was calculated, without altering any of the parameters of the proposed Spectrophotometry technique.

Validity

Recovery studies verified the method's accuracy. Known quantities of the raw material, bilastine and montelukast sodium were included into the previously examined formulation & the process was then carried out in accordance with the analysis of the formulation. It was calculated how much of each medication was found. Each concentration underwent three iterations of this process. Calculated was the % RSD.

Detection Limit

Six calibration curves were performed, and after calculating the standard deviation (SD) of the intercepts, the LOD was determined using the formula.

$$\text{LOD} = (3.3 * \text{SD}) / \text{Slope}$$

SD stands for the Y-intercept standard deviation of the six calibration curves.

The six calibration curves' average slope is referred to as slope.

Limit of Quantitation

Following six calibration curve runs and measurement of the intercepts' standard deviation (SD), the LOQ was calculated using the technique.

LOQ= (10*SD) / Slope

SD stands for the Y-intercept standard deviation of the six calibration curves.

The six calibration curves' average slope is referred to as slope.

METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS EQUATION

Simultaneous Analysis technique based on the medication MONT and BILA's maximum levels of absorption. 344 nm (1) and 282 nm (2) are the two wavelengths used for the construction of the simultaneous equation. Both drugs' absorptivities at both wavelengths were identified. Equations for estimating concentration were found using, $C_x = (A_1*y_2) - (A_2*y_1) / x_1y_2 - x_2y_1$ (1)

$$C_y = (A_2*x_1) - (A_1*x_2) / x_1y_2 - x_2y_1$$
..... (2)

Where A1 and A2 denote the sample solution's absorbance at 344 and 282 nm, respectively, and x1 and x2 denote the MONT's absorptivity at 344 nm,

y1 = BILA's absorptivity at 282 nm

Cx and Cy represent the concentrations of MONT and BILA in the sample solution.

y2= Absorptivity of BILA at 282nm

Evaluation of a tablet formulation

Measuring 20 tabs is proceeded by finely powdering them. A 100 ml volumetric flask was filled with powder that had been precisely measured to equal 10 mg of MONT and 20 mg of BILA. The abovementioned flask received a small amount (50 ml) of methanol before being exposed to five minutes of sonication. Using Whatman filter paper and the same solvent, the solution was filtered into a second 100 ml volumetric flask. To synthesize 8 g/ml of MONT and 16 g/ml of BILA the required amount was elevated using methanol after the appropriate percentage was put to a 10 ml volumetric flask. Solution spectra between 400 and 200 nm were studied, and at 282 and 344 nm, the solution's absorbance was calculated. In parallel equations (1) and (2), absorbance at these two wavelengths was substituted to calculate the amount of medicine present (2).

FINAL RESULTS & Analysis

The recommended methods received approval in accordance with ICH recommendations. It was found that when the absorbances of MONT and BILA were plotted against their respective concentrations, the graphs were linear in the concentration ranges of 2–12 g/ml and 4–24 g/ml, respectively. The correlation coefficients for the two medications using the

simultaneous equation method were 0.9999 at 344 nm and 0.9994 at 282 nm. For both of the medications listed in Table 1, precision was determined as interday and intraday fluctuations, and % RSD was discovered to be less than 2. The accuracy of the approach was evaluated at levels of 50%, 100%, and 150%. For MONT and BILA, respectively, the percentage recovery for this technique varies from 99.33 to 100.34% and 99.52 to 100.07%, as shown in Table 2. The LOD and LOQ for MONT and BILA, respectively, are 0.21 and 0.63 and 0.44 and 1.29. The approach may be utilised effectively to estimate MONT and BILA simultaneously in a combination tablet dose form. Marketed pills were examined, and the results ranged from 98 to 102%. (Table 3).

Table 1. Validation Parameters for simultaneous equation method

Parameters	Montelukast Sodium	Bilastine
$\lambda_{max}(nm)$	344	282
Linearity range ($\mu g/ml$)	2-12	4-24
Correlation Coefficient	0.9999	0.9994
Accuracy	% RSD	
Repeatability	0.32%	0.41%
Intraday	0.18-0.80%	0.28-0.42%
Interday	0.18-0.29%	0.24-0.68%
% Recovery	99.33-100.34%	99.52-100.07%
LOD	0.21	0.44
LOQ	0.63	1.29

Table 2. % Recovery Studies for Montelukast Sodium and Bilastine

% Spiking	Test Conc. ($\mu g/ml$)	Std Conc. ($\mu g/ml$)	Total conc. ($\mu g/ml$)	Amt of drug found ($\mu g/ml$)	Amt of drug recovered ($\mu g/ml$)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery $\pm$ SD
Montelukast Sodium							
50	4	2	6	6.07	4.07	101.17	100.34 $\pm$ 1.892969
	4	2	6	5.89	3.89	98.17	
	4	2	6	6.10	4.10	101.67	
100	4	4	8	8.05	4.05	100.62	99.33 $\pm$ 1.119062
	4	4	8	7.90	3.90	98.75	
	4	4	8	7.89	3.89	98.62	
150	4	6	10	10.10	4.10	101.00	100.23 $\pm$ 0.665833
	4	6	10	9.98	3.98	99.80	
	4	6	10	9.99	3.99	99.90	
Bilastine							
50	8	4	12	11.85	7.85	98.75	99.52 $\pm$ 0.692556
	8	4	12	11.97	7.97	99.75	
	8	4	12	12.01	8.01	100.08	
100	8	8	16	16.03	8.03	100.18	99.57 $\pm$ 0.626126
	8	8	16	15.83	7.83	98.93	
	8	8	16	15.94	7.94	99.62	
150	8	12	20	20.01	8.01	100.05	100.07 $\pm$ 0.175594
	8	12	20	20.05	8.05	100.25	
	8	12	20	19.98	7.98	99.90	

Table 3. Assay of marketed formulation (n=3)

Drug name	Labelled claim (mg)	Conc. taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Conc. found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Assay $\pm$ SD
Montelukast Sodium	10	8	8.15	101.83% $\pm$ 0.069282
Bilastine	20	16	15.97	99.79% $\pm$ 0.034641

CONCLUSION:

For the combined dose estimate of MONT and BILA, a simultaneous equation technique has been proposed. The approach was analysed and determined to be straightforward, diplomatic, accurate, and exact. In comparison to chromatographic techniques, simultaneous equation approaches provide a number of advantages, including as simplicity, quicker turnaround times, and lower costs. The technique worked well for determining the total dose of MONT and BILA.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The Parul Institute of Pharmacy and Research, Faculty of Pharmacy, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India, supplied the resources required to finish the work, and the authors are very appreciative of their assistance.

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